

METHODS FOR FORMING THINKING AND COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Norinboyeva Durdonaxon Janobiddin qizi

FarDU 3-bosqich talabasi

durdonakhonnorinboeva@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

This article talked about one of the ways to learn critical thinking about the principles of thinking and communication in foreign languages, which describe this process.

Modern conditions of the development of society set new goals for us education system. The most important of them is freedom and formation an active person capable of making deliberate, balanced decisions. Today, the republic needs specialists who can think creatively and have the latest achievements technologies capable of starting and implementing projects on an international scale degree. Therefore, knowledge of foreign languages is a mandatory component personal and professional self-awareness of the specialist. In this regard, the interest in new pedagogical paradigms is not accidental. Special attention is paid in some pedagogical researches in recent years teaching mental skills, cognitive research processes. There is critical thinking is the basis for the development of intellectual abilities. Can be any language acquired during active interaction. In this regard, critical thinking plays a very important role in the effective development of a foreign language, because we are engaged. It is a problem that needs to be formulated and find an original solution correct and precise, in other words, a creative approach. The task of pedagogy and psychology is to educate an active person can think and act independently, not only following generally accepted information the rules. Rejection of pedagogical authoritarianism, one-sidedness in assessment what is happening required various scientific researches in the educational system, among them, the problem of developing mental abilities takes an important place number of students. Teachers have long recognized the importance of teaching.¹ The focus should be on students'

1. ¹ Turchin V.F. Phenomenon of Science: A Cybernetic Approach to Evolution.- 2nd ed.— M.: ETS.- 2000. - 368 p.

assimilation of the information presented and mastery rather than mechanical memorization of the learning material student thinking. Goals and tasks of education in the 21st century variable, because further data collection causes overload the task of students and the teacher is not to generalize knowledge, but to equip it the student has a tool that can be used to acquire this knowledge independently. Developing critical thinking has been one of the goals of education generally recognized in foreign pedagogy for decades. As you know, at the moment intellectual development of a person is not determined by the amount knowledge, information stored in memory, amount of scientific information, but with man's readiness to choose by analyzing the necessary knowledge, the ability to understand information and make decisions independently.

The current social situation posed the problem of student formation. critical thinking was qualitatively new and demanded pedagogy revision of the content of this concept. The purpose of teaching thinking is to encourage the promotion of innovation ideas that destroy the usual stereotypes and generally accepted views, teaching students are active, alternative, rational, at the same time irrational choice problem solving techniques and methods. The term "critical thinking" has been around for a very long time. The works of famous psychologists such as J. Piaget, J. Bruner, L.S. Vygotsky. This concept exists in the professional language of practicing teachers used relatively recently. Currently, different scientific sources can find different definitions critical thinking. Modern researchers define this concept as a process of consciousness understands established ideas, processes information to create new ideas; or problem solving. David Kluster's description fully reveals the essence of this species thinking. According to David Kluster, the definition consists of five points. First, critical thinking is independent. Therefore, there should be critical thinking individual in nature. Second, information is not the end point of criticality, but the starting point thinking. Third, critical thinking begins with asking questions and clarifying problems to be solved. Fourth, critical thinking must involve sound thinking. A critical learner looks for unique ways to solve problems solves the problem and supports this decision with reasonable arguments. He also tries to prove the correctness of his decision through various mental operations and presenting the facts. Fifth, critical thinking is social thinking. Every idea is tested and when it is shared with others, or refined, like the philosopher Hannah Arendt writes that someone's existence is necessary for perfection. Therefore, teachers work in accordance with critical thinking, always try to use pairs and different types group work in their classes, including debates and discussions, as well as variety types of publication of student writings. Russian researchers are coming their definitions of "critical thinking".² They interpret it as the ability to analyze information in terms of a logical and personal psychological approach to apply the obtained results to standard and non-standard situations, questions and problems. Consider a specific situation: a student is told "Technological is development a boon or a disaster for future generations?" The question itself very controversial, it has many solutions. The student begins to work independently find a solution to this problem considering that

2. ² Kluster D. What is critical thinking?// Change: Intern magazine about the development of thinking through reading and writing.- 2001. - No. 4. - S. 36-40.

technology development has its own pros and cons in the country and country of the language being studied:

Positive aspects:

- makes human life much easier;
- saves time;
- the Internet provides access to the whole world;
- you can find any information in a few seconds;
- transport allows fast movement on any route;
- you can contact any person of interest to us using a mobile phone;
- satellite TV offers a variety of programs for every taste;
- opportunities are being created to learn a foreign language with the help of foreign TV channels;
- conditions for distance education are created;
- you can find friends from different countries by e-mail;
- virtual conversations, you can hold discussions in a foreign language on the Internet.

Negative aspects:

- gases hazardous to health are released in the transport;
- TV affects the eyes;
- toxic gases are the cause of the greenhouse effect;
- seas, oceans are polluted with oil;
- environmental pollution leads to shortening of human life;
- there is a trend of addiction to virtual life;
- the natural balance is disturbed;
- interferes with live communication

based on his own reasoning, the student expresses his opinion. It may be inside supporting the development of technology or denying its achievements. A student tries to explain everything in a foreign language. Therefore, not only thinking develops, but also the skills of speaking a foreign language. There is no process for completing tasks for the development of critical thinking passive perception of the material and its reproduction, but active student participation during the lesson.

There are four key things you need to know to teach critical thinking principles that describe this process. Each of these principles can be seen as thinking skills: identifying and challenging assumptions; check for authenticity clarity and logical consistency; consider the context; to discover alternatives. The characteristic features of developed critical thinking are: evaluation, value side of assessment, openness to new ideas, reflection grounds for his critical judgment. Teaching critical thinking activities includes acquiring skills such as:

- ability to use arguments in disputes;
- the ability to look at old ideas from a new perspective;
- distinguish facts from assumptions;
- the ability to distinguish logical judgment from emotion one;
- the ability to identify cause-and-effect relationships, if any; errors in them;

- the ability to see inconsistencies and errors in the studied material and find smart ways to eliminate them.

For the student to take advantage of his opportunities. It is important that he develops a number of important qualities, among them D. Halpern separately [3]: willingness to plan, while organizing chaotic thoughts is important and distribute them in a certain sequence, this is a sign of trust;

- the flexibility needed to listen to the student's ideas others, enriching his mental potential. Only then can judgment begin on a specific question;
- perseverance - which is needed when faced with a difficult task often forcing students to postpone its solution until a later date. Through development perseverance in the tension of the mind, the student achieves positive results in learning;
- willingness to correct mistakes: a person who is able to think a critic always admits his mistakes, analyzes them, draws certain conclusions for himself;
- awareness is a very important quality and it includes ability observing oneself in the process of mental activity, observing its progress thinking;
- involves the ability to find compromise solutions alternative solutions that are easy to perceive by other people.

The level of criticality is determined not only by the stock of knowledge and skills that a person has, as well as his personal qualities, mental relationships and many aspects of his beliefs, including reflective skills attitude to his "I", moral and social responsibility, respect for the individual features. every person. Among the listed qualities, it is one of the main ones impartiality of judgment expressed in the relentless pursuit of individual search for truth, criticism for truth. The highest level of formation of critical thinking means the presence of integration mental abilities based on logical, problem-solving, critical synthesis thinking and from these powers practical, professional and social activity. At the same time, it is important: to be able to identify prejudices; transfer of knowledge to each other; determine the effect of this problem solving knowledge, which comes with questions:

- What do I know?
- What did I learn?
- How has my knowledge changed?
- What do I do about it?

Thus, the task of developing critical thinking, according to R. Paul, for that students strive to overcome the tendency to consider their opinion and worth directions, as the only important and correct ones, which are relevant a manifestation of a person's natural inclination. It should be noted that critical thinking helps to fully master a foreign language, starting from the student is involved in the learning process and is an active participant to show their views about a particular problem. Along with the thought process, foreign language teaching skills develop because the student not only to express their thoughts creatively, to show their understanding, to share their thoughts, to argue, to argue, but also to be able to form a speech in a foreign language. Unlike him traditional forms of learning, critical thinking helps to assimilate foreign language material is more effective, because this type includes everything thinking mechanisms such as analysis, synthesis, generalization,

estimation, competition. A student not only listens, speaks, reads or writes, but also "absorbs" necessary material. Information does not become passive knowledge, but becomes it active part. Learning a foreign language always involves a critical process thinking is one of the main criteria.

References:

1. Dushatova, S., & Azamov, M. (2022, November). SO'Z TURKUMLARI TASNIFI. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 6, pp. 89-95).
2. Dushatova, S., & Tursunaliyev, M. (2022). CHET TILLARINI O'RGANISHNING INSON RIVOJLANISHIGA TASIRI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT IN THE GLOBAL SCIENCE, 1(7), 133-138.
3. Kluster D. What is critical thinking?// Change: Intern.magazine about the development of thinking through reading and writing.- 2001. - No. 4. - S. 36-40.
4. Turchin V.F. Phenomenon of Science: A Cybernetic Approach to Evolution.- 2nd ed.— M.: ETS.- 2000. - 368 p.
5. Halpern D. Psychology of critical thinking. Ser. "Masters of Psychology".- St. Petersburg: Peter, 2000.
6. Homolova, E. (2004). A lesson around job adverts. New York: McGraw-Hill.
7. Jacobson, E. Degener, S. & Purcell-Gates, V. (2003). Creating authentic materials and activities for the adult literacy classroom: A handbook for practitioners. USA: NCSALL. 57
8. Kennedy, E.C. (1981). Method in teaching development reading (2nd d.). USA: F.E, Peacock Publisher, inc.
9. Kilickaya, F. (2013). Authentic materials and cultural content in EFL classroom, (pp. 75-92).
10. Kustaryo, S. (1998). Reading techniques for college students. Jakarta: P2LPTK.
11. Thanajaro, M. (2000). Using authentic materials to develop listening comprehension in the English as a second language classroom. Dissertation submitted to the Faculty of the Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, Blacksburg, Virginia.